

Wikipedia e la Fabbrica delle Citazioni (Citogenesi)

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Cosa è la citogenesi (citogenesis in Inglese):

<https://web.archive.org/web/20250323082159/https://min.cartongesso.xyz/Portfolio/Prints/Tabù.pdf>

“Quando un utente scrive qualcosa su Wikipedia senza citarla, questa informazione potrebbe venire captata da, ad esempio, un giornalista frettoloso. La stessa informazione così riproposta su una fonte di informazioni ritenuta attendibile, una testata giornalistica per l'appunto. Quindi ora il ciclo si può chiudere: l'originale informazione (non veritiera) su Wikipedia ha ora una fonte da citare e sembrare a tutti gli effetti un fatto comprovato e per nulla inventato a tavolino. Questo fenomeno è conosciuto con il nome di citogenesis”. Schema in inglese <https://imgs.xkcd.com/comics/citogenesis.png>

Ed ecco <https://slate.com/technology/2019/03/wikipedia-citogenesis-circular-reporting-problem.html>

<https://web.archive.org/web/20250323084752/https://slate.com/technology/2019/03/wikipedia-citogenesis-circular-reporting-problem.html>

“The Internet’s Dizzying Citogenesis Problem. Circular reporting is a real problem on platforms like Wikipedia—and it’s harder to solve than it looks.” Di Stephen Harrison, 2019.

“Two weeks ago, Dr. James Heilman discovered something strange. ... [he] noticed that DrugBank, an online database for drug information, was copying text directly from Wikipedia. Although Heilman considers Wikipedia’s medical content to be of surprisingly good quality, he was concerned—because he didn’t just find DrugBank copying and citing Wikipedia; he had also found several examples of Wikipedia likewise copying and citing DrugBank. For example, the DrugBank page for protamine sulfate, a medication often used in heart surgery, included information taken from the medication’s Wikipedia page. But the medication’s Wikipedia page cited the medication’s DrugBank page. This circular referencing created a problem for proving the veracity of the information found on the Wikipedia page—where was the original source material really from? Could it be trusted? Heilman found five other Wikipedia articles about medications with similarly circular references, and he speculated that there could be many more. He contacted DrugBank about the issues, and they are working to resolve them. Meanwhile, Heilman (known by the Wikipedia username “Doc James”) expressed concern on the WikiProject Medicine talk page—the forum where Wikipedia editors discuss improvements to articles about medicine and health—that “citogenesis has become a reality.” [Harrison, 2019]

“The most infamous cases of citogenesis are those that resulted in the widespread distribution of a falsehood in news media. ... In December 2016, an anonymous user edited Secretary of State Mike Pompeo’s Wikipedia page to state that Pompeo had served in the Gulf War. The false claim was repeated in outlets such as the Wall Street Journal and the New Yorker until, in April 2018, the CIA confirmed that Pompeo did not in fact serve in the Gulf War.” [Harrison, 2019]

“Of course, if a reporter writes an article based on flawed information from Wikipedia, they bear the responsibility for the inaccuracy. Relying on Wikipedia as an independent source is simply bad journalistic practice. The online encyclopedia explicitly states that it does not guarantee the validity

of information contained on the site, which is maintained by a community of volunteer editors and not subject to a formal review process. But, at the same time, the practical reality is that millions of internet users (not just journalists) rely on Wikipedia for information. And because the nonprofit Wikimedia Foundation says it aims for Wikimedia projects to become the essential infrastructure of free and trustworthy knowledge, it makes sense for the movement to at least consider some countermeasures to reduce the risk of misinformation being spread by circular reporting.” [Harrison, 2019].

Harrison realized, “after corresponding with Wikipedian Liam Wyatt” that “the solution to the citogenesis problem may not be so simple”. “Like a lot of Wikipedians, Wyatt has his favorite example of the phenomenon: the “Stalin’s bathroom” incident, which shows just how sticky the problem can get. In February 2009, an anonymous editor changed the German Wikipedia page for Karl-Marx-Allee (a major boulevard in Berlin) to claim that it was known as “Stalin’s bathroom,” implying it was the Soviet dictator’s toilet. Multiple publications repeated this bad information. Feeling guilty, the Wikipedia editor who created the fake nickname tried to remove the bad information—however, when he tried, other editors reversed his change because there were “reliable” citations for it”.

Tornando al testo in italiano, cito ancora: “chiunque ha finito la prima elementare sa che non dovrebbe utilizzare Wikipedia come fonte per una tesi o qualsiasi genere di contenuto divulgativo, o perlomeno lo sappiamo come dogma, senza saperne precisamente il perché. Innanzitutto, Wikipedia non è una fonte primaria di informazioni, è una enciclopedia, è la somma complessiva della conoscenza umana consolidata come vera.” ATTENZIONE: “consolidata come vera? Wikipedia? Altre enciclopedie, come la Treccani, hanno un’altra struttura, e mostrano il nome degli autori. C’è enciclopedia ed enciclopedia. In ogni caso si DEVE avere un approccio critico e controllare. Assumere Wikipedia come enciclopedia della conoscenza umana consolidata come vera è decisamente una forzatura.

Torniamo alla citogenesi. Come discusso da Harrison, 2019, è persino impossibile per un editor correggere i banchi d’informazione. Un altro editor, per svariate possibili ragioni, che possono essere anche tendenziose e di parte, blocca il primo editor e riporta a versione precedente. Dalla lettura dell’articolo di Harrison si evince che il problema della citazione circolare non è risolvibile. Esiste anche un ulteriore problema, quello che Wikipedia lascia ‘maturare’ le voci, confidando in un miglioramento continuo di esse. Wikipedia chiede infatti di collaborare.

Si potrebbe pensare che basti non usare più Wikipedia. Se si interroga il web su un argomento, Wikipedia ci viene presentata in posizione rilevante. Ed esiste AI.

Alla domanda “Is AI affected by citogenesis?”, AI risponde Yes, in particolare un large linguistic model “can be affected by "citogenesis." Le ragioni sono le seguenti.

“LLMs are trained on massive datasets of text and code from the internet. If these datasets contain instances of "citogenesis" (false information that has gained credibility through circular reporting), the AI can learn and perpetuate those falsehoods”. “AI models learn patterns and relationships from their training data. If they encounter a piece of misinformation cited by multiple sources, they may incorrectly assign a high degree of confidence to that information”. “When an AI generates text, it draws upon the patterns it has learned. If it has absorbed "citogenesis," it can reproduce and even amplify the misinformation, further contributing to its spread”.

“AI can create outputs that appear very confident and authoritative, which could lead people to accept false information as true”. “The sheer volume of information that AI processes makes it difficult to

detect and correct every instance of "citogenesis."” “As AI becomes more integrated into information gathering and dissemination, the potential for it to be a vector for "citogenesis" increases”.

“Therefore, AI is not immune to the problems of information reliability, and there are serious concerns about AI contributing to the spread of misinformation via the citogenesis effect. There is ongoing research and work being done to mitigate these effects.”

Ti senti di poter essere manipolata?

“Yes, the potential for manipulation of AI, including LLMs like myself, is a significant concern. Here's a breakdown of the key aspects:

Data Poisoning: Malicious actors could intentionally introduce biased or false data into the training datasets of AI models. This "poisoning" could lead the AI to generate outputs that reflect those biases or falsehoods.

Prompt Engineering: Skilled manipulators can craft prompts that elicit desired (and potentially harmful) responses from AI. This can be used to generate propaganda, misinformation, or other forms of deceptive content.

Deepfakes and Synthetic Media: AI-generated deepfakes and synthetic media can be used to create highly realistic but false videos, audio recordings, and images. These can be used to spread misinformation, damage reputations, or incite violence.

Algorithmic Bias: Even without malicious intent, AI models can inherit biases from their training data. This can lead to discriminatory or unfair outcomes in areas such as loan applications, hiring decisions, and criminal justice.

Automation of Disinformation: AI can automate the generation and dissemination of disinformation at a massive scale, making it much harder to detect and counter.

Lack of Transparency: The "black box" nature of some AI models makes it difficult to understand how they arrive at their conclusions, which can make it harder to identify and correct manipulation.

Therefore, the problem is not just that AI can be manipulated, but that the manipulation can be very difficult to detect, and can have far reaching consequences.”

Attenti al lupo!